

Influence of clinical pharmacist counseling on tamoxifen-related knowledge and adherence among women with breast cancer

Hala Saad Bash¹, Ihsan Salah Rabea²

¹ Department of Pharmacognosy, College of Pharmacy, University of Babylon, Hillah, Iraq

² Department of Clinical Pharmacy, College of Pharmacy, University of Kufa, Al-Najaf, Iraq

Corresponding author: Hala Saad Bash (hala.saad@uobabylon.edu.iq; hala.bash@student.uokufa.edu.iq)

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Abstract

Seventy women with breast cancer who visited the center monthly to receive tamoxifen were randomized into two groups: a control group, which received the standard course of treatment, and an intervention group, which received the standard course of treatment in addition to pharmacy consultations. A statistically significant difference in knowledge scores was observed between the control and intervention groups at three months post-intervention ($P < 0.001$). Furthermore, a significant improvement in knowledge scores was noted within the intervention group when comparing baseline and three months post-intervention scores ($P < 0.001$). A significant improvement in adherence scores was also observed within the intervention group between baseline and three months post-intervention ($P < 0.001$). Additionally, a statistically significant difference in adherence scores was found between the control and intervention groups at three months post-intervention ($P < 0.001$). Our findings demonstrated a noticeable improvement in the knowledge and adherence levels of participants as a result of pharmacy consultation.

Keywords

adherence, breast cancer, clinical pharmacist, knowledge, tamoxifen

Introduction

In Asia, the proportion of women diagnosed with hormone-positive breast cancer (BC) is 50% (Roheel et al. 2023). The effective treatment for hormone-positive BC is tamoxifen, a selective estrogen receptor modulator (SERM) used as adjuvant and preventive therapy for women with BC (Goldstein 2022; Al-Matrafi et al. 2024). Although the suggested treatment duration is five years, some studies have suggested that extending treatment for up to 10 years reduces the risk of disease recurrence and enhances quality of life (Mamounas et al. 2024; Navarro-Sabate et al. 2024; Ito et al. 2025). While extended

treatment improves the quality of life for women with BC, it may also hinder adherence to therapy (Religioni et al. 2025). The rate of adherence to endocrine therapy among women with BC is suboptimal, ranging from 33.3% to 88.6%. Moreover, for each year of therapy, there is a 25.5% reduction in adherence (Pezzolato et al. 2023). Adherence to treatment is influenced by multiple factors, including the disease itself, patients' socio-demographic characteristics, the complexity of the treatment regimen, and communication between patients and healthcare providers (HCPs) (Stewart et al. 2023). Poor communication between patients and HCPs contributes to lower adherence rates among women with BC due to reduced belief

in the necessity of oral anticancer therapy (Sutton et al. 2020). Our study aimed to assess the impact of clinical pharmacist counseling on the knowledge and adherence of women with breast cancer receiving tamoxifen.

Methods

A randomized controlled study, including observation and intervention phases, was conducted at the Babylon Oncology Center, Merjan Teaching Hospital, Babil Province, Iraq. The study was carried out during the period from 18 February 2024 to 1 October 2024. A total of seventy female patients were recruited according to inclusion criteria, which included patients aged 18 years or older with a confirmed diagnosis of breast cancer (any stage or grade). Additionally, patients must have been treated with tamoxifen for more than one month and agreed to participate in the study. Patients who were receiving tamoxifen for the first time, had a psychiatric illness, or had any condition compromising their ability to understand information or comply with study procedures were excluded. Women with breast cancer who visited the Babylon Oncology Center monthly to receive tamoxifen and met the inclusion criteria were randomized into two groups: a control group comprising 35 patients who received the standard course of treatment at the oncology center and an intervention group comprising 35 patients who received the same standard treatment as the control group, in addition to pharmacy consultations. During the observation phase, participants completed tailored and validated questionnaires through structured interviews. These questionnaires were designed to assess the patients' socio-demographic and clinical characteristics, as well as their knowledge and adherence to tamoxifen. During the intervention phase, the pharmacy consultations provided to the intervention group involved face-to-face interviews with each patient, lasting approximately 25 minutes. In these sessions, the pharmacist delivered educational information tailored to each patient's specific treatment regimen. At three months post-intervention, changes in knowledge and adherence levels were assessed through follow-up face-to-face interviews conducted with both the control and intervention groups.

The tamoxifen-related knowledge questionnaire was developed based on a thorough literature review using databases (Kim et al. 2015; Milata et al. 2018; Saghatchian and Lesur 2019; Thorneloe et al. 2020; Hammarström et al. 2023). The questionnaire consisted of 16 items (see Suppl. material 1). Regarding the scoring, the total score ranged from 0 to 16. For items 1 to 14 and item 16, a score of 1 was assigned for the answer "Yes," which represented a correct response, while a score of 0 was assigned for the answers "No" or "Do not know," which were considered incorrect. For item 15, a score of 1 was assigned for a "Yes" response to either of the two points, as each represented a correct answer. The level of knowledge was evaluated using established cut-off points (Yusof et al. 2014; Shallo and Boru 2019; Abdelaziz et al. 2021; Said et al. 2022; Oufi and Rabea 2023). Total knowledge scores were obtained

by summing the individual item scores and classified into three categories: low, moderate, and high level of knowledge; a score of 0 to 8 indicated a low knowledge; a score of 8.16 to 11.2 indicated a moderate knowledge; and a score of 11.36 to 16 indicated a high knowledge.

The treatment adherence questionnaire consisted of 10 items (see Suppl. material 1) and used a binary scale with "Yes" and "No" responses. Each "Yes" response was assigned a score of 0, and each "No" response a score of 1, except for item 5, where "Yes" was scored as 1 and "No" as 0. Total adherence scores were calculated by summing the individual item scores and were categorized into three levels: a score of 0 to 5.9 indicated a low adherence; a score of 6 to 7 indicated a moderate adherence; and a score of 8 to 10 indicated a high adherence (Tomaszewski et al. 2017; Stahlschmidt et al. 2019; Qedair et al. 2022; Jawad Suker and Hussein 2024).

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was conducted using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 24. To measure internal consistency, Cronbach's alpha was calculated. Categorical variables (nominal or ordinal) were presented as frequencies and percentages. Numerical variables (discrete or continuous) were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) for normally distributed data and as median \pm interquartile range (IQR) for non-normally distributed data. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used to assess the normality distribution. For non-normally distributed data, the Mann-Whitney U test was used to assess within-group differences at baseline and at 12 weeks post-intervention. The pilot study demonstrated consistent responses, and the Cronbach's alpha value exceeded 0.7. The study was approved by the Scientific and Ethical Committee of the Faculty of Medicine, Kufa University (Ref. No. MEC-18, dated 14/02/2024). Informed consent was obtained from all eligible participants after a detailed explanation of the study's purpose was provided.

Results

Sociodemographic and clinical characteristics of participants at baseline

The control and intervention groups comprised the two study arms. Breast cancer women receiving tamoxifen were randomly assigned to either the control or intervention group, with 35 patients in each group. Both groups were comparable in mean age and marital status, with p-values of 0.726 and 0.565, respectively. No statistically significant differences were observed between the groups in terms of educational level, residency, or employment status ($P > 0.05$), as illustrated in Table 1.

The control and intervention groups were similar in terms of exposure to radiation ($P = 1$) and type of breast removal surgery ($P = 0.693$). No statistically significant differences were observed between the groups regarding

Table 1. Sociodemographic characteristics of participants at baseline.

Variable	Control group (n = 35)		Intervention group (n = 35)		*P.value	
	No.	%	No.	%		
Age (year)	≤40	10	28.6	9	25.7	0.539
	41–50	22	62.8	22	62.8	
	51–60	2	5.7	3	8.6	
	≥ 61	1	2.9	1	2.9	
	Mean (SD)	43.71 (7.2)		45.03 (7.6)		
Marital status	Single	3	8.6	4	11.4	0.565
	Married	31	88.6	31	88.6	
	Widowed	1	2.9	0	0	
Educational level	Illiterate	2	5.7	1	2.9	0.468
	Primary	18	51.4	21	60	
	Secondary	5	14.3	7	20	
	Bachelor degree	10	28.6	5	14.3	
	Higher education	0	0.0	1	2.9	
Residency	Urban	14	40	11	31.4	0.454
	Rural	21	60	24	68.6	
Employment	Yes	9	25.7	6	17.1	0.382
	No	26	74.3	29	82.9	

*Statistically significant ($P < 0.05$) according to Fisher's exact test and chi-square test.

history of infertility, presence of family history of disease, stage of breast cancer, or histological type ($P > 0.05$). The mean duration of treatment was 28.3 months for the control group and 30.3 months for the intervention group, with no statistically significant difference between the two groups. When comparing the presence of chronic diseases other than breast cancer, the control group showed a higher percentage of patients with hypertension (20%). In the intervention group, 8.6% of patients had gastric ulcers, and 5.7% had either hypertension or diabetes. Both groups included patients who suffered from depression. A statistically significant difference was observed in the number of drugs used for chronic diseases other than anticancer therapy between the two groups, as shown in Table 2.

Impact of pharmacist intervention on knowledge scores among women with breast cancer

Knowledge scores of the participants were assessed at baseline (during the observation phase) and again at 12 weeks (three months) to evaluate the impact of pharmacist-led education and intervention among women with breast cancer receiving tamoxifen. At baseline, the median score on the knowledge scale among the 70 women receiving tamoxifen was 6.9 out of 16, with an interquartile range (IQR) of 6 to 7.4. Among the participants, 21.4% demonstrated a moderate level of knowledge, while 78.6% exhibited a low level of knowledge regarding the tamoxifen regimen, proper use, drug interactions, side effects, contraindications, and recommended follow-up duration with an oncologist (Fig. 1). After three months of intervention, the median score increased to 8.14 out of 16, with an interquartile range (IQR) of 6.7 to 11.18. Among the 70 participants, 21.4% demonstrated a high level of knowledge, and 31.4% ($n = 22$) achieved a moderate level of knowledge. Although a substantial proportion (47.2%) still exhibited a

low level of knowledge, this represented a notable decrease compared to the pre-intervention phase (Fig. 1).

A statistically significant difference in knowledge scores was observed between the control and intervention groups at three months post-intervention ($P < 0.001$). Furthermore, a significant improvement in knowledge scores was noted within the intervention group when comparing baseline and three months post-intervention scores ($P < 0.001$). However, no significant change in knowledge scores was observed within the control group between baseline and three months post-intervention ($P = 0.081$) (Table 3).

Figure 1. Tamoxifen-related knowledge levels at baseline and three months post-pharmacist intervention.

Impact of pharmacist intervention on adherence score of breast cancer women

Adherence scores of the studied patients were assessed at baseline (during the observation phase) and again at 12 weeks (three months) to evaluate the impact of pharmacist-led education and intervention on women

Table 2. Clinical characteristics of participants at baseline.

Variable	Control group (n = 35)		Intervention group (n = 35)		*P.value	
	No.	%	No.	%		
History of infertility	Yes	11	31.4	9	25.7	0.597
	No	24	68.6	26	74.3	
Family History	1 st degree	15	42.9	11	31.4	0.598
	2 nd degree	9	25.7	10	28.6	
Stage of breast cancer	No history	11	31.4	14	40	0.518
	Stage 0	2	5.7	0	0	
	Stage I	3	8.6	4	11.4	
	Stage II	19	54.3	21	60	
	Stage III	10	28.6	10	28.6	
Histology of breast cancer	Stage IV	1	2.9	0	0	0.478
	Luminal A	26	74.3	26	74.3	
	Luminal B (HER2 negative)	2	5.7	4	11.4	
	Luminal B (HER2 positive)	7	20	4	11.4	
Breast removal	DCIS	0	0	1	2.9	0.693
	Non	1	2.9	2	5.7	
	BCS+Ac	17	48.6	19	54.3	
Breast radiation	MRM+Ac	17	48.6	14	40	1
	Yes	27	77.1	27	77.1	
Duration of treatment (months)	No	8	22.9	8	22.9	0.285
	Maximum		84		72	
	Minimum		2		3	
Comorbidities	Mean (SD)		28.3(30.3)		30.3(17.6)	
	Diabetes mellitus	5	14.3	2	5.7	0.232
Hypertension	7	20	2	5.7	0.07	
Hepatitis B	1	2.9	0	0	0.314	
Depression	1	2.9	1	2.9	1	
Gastric ulcer	2	5.7	3	8.6	0.643	
Glaucoma	1	2.9	0	0	0.314	
Thromboembolism	1	2.9	0	0	0.314	
Endometrial hyperplasia	1	2.9	0	0	0.314	
Anemia	0	0	1	2.9	0.314	
Hyperthyroidism	1	2.9	0	0	0.314	
Electrocardiopathy	0	0	1	2.9	0.314	
Polycystic ovarian syndrome	0	0	1	2.9	0.314	
GI disturbance	0	0	1	2.9	0.314	
The number of the medications, other than anticancer drugs						
Non	18	51.4	28	80	0.015	
1 drug	17	48.6	6	17.1		
2–5 drugs	0	0	1	2.9		

*Statistically significant ($P < 0.05$) according to Fisher's exact test and chi-square test.

Table 3. Comparison of knowledge scores between control and intervention groups at baseline and three months post-intervention.

	Control group (n = 35)	Intervention group (n = 35)	*P.value
	Median (IQR)	Median (IQR)	
Knowledge score at baseline	6.9 (6–7.3)	7 (6–8.18)	0.79
Knowledge score post 3 months	7 (6–7.8)	11.18 (10.25–12.11)	< 0.001
**P.value	0.081	< 0.001	
Z value		6.639	
Effect size		0.79	Large

*Statistically significant (p -value < 0.05) according to the Mann-Whitney U test; **statistically significant (p -value < 0.05) according to the Wilcoxon signed-ranks test.

with breast cancer receiving tamoxifen. Among seventy women with breast cancer receiving tamoxifen, the median score was 5.5 out of 10 with an interquartile range (IQR) of 4 to 7. Among the participants, 10% demonstrated a high adherence level, while 40% exhibited a moderate adherence level. However, 35 out of 70 participants (50%) demonstrated a low adherence level at baseline (Fig. 2). Following three months of intervention, the median score increased to 6.5 out of 10, with an IQR of 5 to 8. Among the 70 participants, 27.1% demonstrated a high level of adherence. Additionally, 30 participants (42.9%) achieved a moderate level of adherence. Moreover, 30% of participants exhibited a low level of adherence; however, this percentage was lower compared to the pre-intervention phase (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Tamoxifen-related adherence levels at baseline and three-month post-pharmacist intervention.

A significant improvement in adherence scores was seen within the intervention group when comparing baseline and three months post-intervention scores ($P < 0.001$). Furthermore, a statistically significant difference in adherence scores was observed between the control and intervention groups at three months post-intervention ($P < 0.001$). However, no significant change in adherence scores was observed within the control group between baseline and three months post-intervention ($P = 0.096$) (Table 4).

Discussion

Knowledge of oral anticancer therapy – including its benefits, mechanism of action, treatment regimen, potential adverse effects, drug-drug interactions, and drug-food interactions – significantly influences adherence among women with breast cancer. Consequently, this adherence impacts overall health outcomes (Adamowicz and Baczkowska-Waliszewska 2020). Our study revealed that 21.4% of 70 patients receiving tamoxifen demonstrated a moderate level of knowledge. However, a high proportion of patients (78.6%) exhibited a low level of knowledge regarding tamoxifen. This finding suggests that patient knowledge may be associated with various factors, including complexity of treatment, patient educational level, health literacy, and frequency of appointments with healthcare providers. This finding aligns with that of Thorneloe and colleagues, who reported a low level of knowledge regarding the benefits and risks of tamoxifen among women with breast cancer (Thorneloe et al. 2020).

There was an improvement in knowledge scores in the intervention group, as indicated by a statistically significant difference when comparing baseline and three months post-intervention scores ($P < 0.001$). In parallel, our findings showed a statistically significant difference in knowledge scores between the control and intervention groups at three months post-intervention ($P < 0.001$), with a large effect size. Several studies have indicated the role of clinical pharmacists in improving patient knowledge through education about drug mechanisms, medication regimens, potential adverse effects, and possible interactions between oral anticancer therapy and medications taken for comorbid diseases (Abdelaziz et al. 2021; Moukafih et al. 2021; Pirolli et al. 2022; Alkashaf and Mohammed 2024; Dierkes et al. 2024). Another study on breast cancer outpatients receiving a combination of cyclin-dependent kinase 4/6 inhibitors and oral endocrine therapy highlighted the importance of pharmaceutical intervention in improving health outcomes through management of therapy side effects and enhanced adherence counseling (Patel et al. 2023).

Adherence to oral anticancer therapy is critical for improving survival rates, preventing recurrence, and reducing hospitalization. However, factors such as long therapy duration (especially hormonal endocrine therapy), poor com-

Table 4. Comparison of adherence scores of tamoxifen-receiving breast cancer women between control and intervention groups at baseline and at three months post-intervention.

	Control group (n = 35)	Intervention group (n = 35)	*P.value
	Median (IQR)	Median (IQR)	
Adherence score at baseline	6 (4 -7)	5 (4 -7)	0.894
Adherence score post 3 months	6 (5 -7)	7 (6 -8)	< 0.001
**P.value	0.096	< 0.001	
Z value		4.055	
Effect size		0.48	large

*Statistically significant (p-value < 0.05) according to the Mann-Whitney U test; **Statistically significant (p-value < 0.05) according to the Wilcoxon signed ranks test.

munication with healthcare providers, patient beliefs about therapy, forgetfulness, adverse medication effects, cancer stage, comorbidities, and treatment complexity contribute to suboptimal adherence (Willis et al. 2024). Among participants, 10% demonstrated a high adherence level, while 40% showed moderate adherence to tamoxifen treatment. Our findings indicated that adherence to tamoxifen remains suboptimal, with half of participants demonstrating low adherence at baseline. This aligns with previous studies highlighting challenges with long-term adherence to endocrine therapy among breast cancer patients (Agnew et al. 2024; Assad-Suzuki et al. 2024; Woolpert et al. 2024; Navarro-Sabaté et al. 2025). Conversely, some studies reported higher adherence rates; for example, a retrospective study of 100 women with advanced breast cancer showed high adherence (92.25%) due to effective side effect management (Valerio et al. 2025). Additionally, a systematic review in developing countries on women with nonmetastatic breast cancer demonstrated a 75% adherence rate to endocrine therapy (Elshafie et al. 2025). Our study showed a noticeable improvement in adherence scores following three months of pharmacist intervention. These results are consistent with previous studies indicating that structured interventions may improve adherence levels to prescribed regimens (Jawad Suker and Hussein 2024; Staynova et al. 2024; Karoli and Ganachari 2024). We observed a significant improvement in adherence scores within the intervention group when comparing baseline and three months post-intervention scores ($P < 0.001$). Furthermore, a statistically significant difference in adherence scores was observed between the control and intervention groups at three months post-intervention ($P < 0.001$) (Table 4). This finding is consistent with a previous study showing improvement in adherence scores at 6 and 12 months post-pharmacist intervention among women with breast cancer (Zhu et al. 2024). Similarly, another study highlighted the impact of pharmacists in education and monitoring of adverse effects on adherence levels (Megeed et al. 2023).

Conclusion

This study emphasized significant inadequacies in patient knowledge and adherence regarding prescribed

cancer treatment regimens, particularly among those receiving tamoxifen. Targeted educational interventions significantly enhanced patient knowledge about their treatment regimens, ultimately improving adherence and clinical outcomes. Further studies are recommended to assess and compare medication adherence over 6 and 12 months using various subjective and objective measurement methods to identify factors that motivate long-term medication adherence.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: Scientific and Ethical Committee of Faculty of Medicine/ Kufa University (Ref. No.MEC-18 dated 14/2/2024)

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Author contributions

Both authors have contributed equally.

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

Questionnaires

Authors: Hala Saad Bash, Ihsan Salah Rabea

Data type: docx

Explanation note: Tamoxifen-related knowledge questionnaire and patient adherence questionnaire.

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